
**FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF GASTRODUODENAL
PATHOLOGY IN FULL-TERM AND PREMATURE INFANTS OF EARLY
AGE WITH PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS
SYSTEM**

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Abstract: According to different authors, the frequency of perinatal lesions in premature babies with extremely low body weight ranges from 15-60 to 65-85%. More than 30% of all forms of chronic pathology of adults have their origins in childhood, and the beginning of many of them are vegetative-visceral dysfunctions against the background of perinatal pathology of the central nervous system. The issues of the influence of chronic hypoxia on the functional state of the gastrointestinal tract of a premature baby, as well as the relationship between the lesion of the central nervous system and the disorder of the gastrointestinal tract remain insufficiently studied. A fundamental study of these issues will help to develop methods for the prevention of digestive diseases in old age.

KEY WORDS: central nervous system damage, gastroduodenal pathology, feeding, newborn, constipation.

Introduction

According to domestic and foreign researchers, up to 85% of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) are caused by irrational nutrition in infancy.

As you know, the optimal food for a newborn is mother's milk .Balanced in micro- and macronutrients, proteins, fats and carbohydrates, the composition of breast milk ensures the full growth and development of the child.

The purpose of our study was to study the clinical course of gastroduodenal pathology in full-term and premature babies with perinatal lesions of the central nervous system (CNS) depending on the method of feeding.

Material and methods

The study was conducted on the basis of the Republican Children's Clinical Hospital and Children's Clinical Hospital № 1 g. Makhachkala. The study was based on the results of a prospective clinical examination of 155 children. The first group consisted of 60 full-term children with CNS PP and gastroduodenal pathology. The second group included 45 premature babies with PP CNS and gastroduodenal pathology. The third (control) group was represented by 50 full-term, relatively healthy newborns. To study the risk factors for the development of gastroduodenal pathology and perinatal CNS damage, questionnaire maps were compiled, which were filled out when talking to the parents of the children.

The criterion for including children in the study was the presence of CNS PP and gastroduodenal pathology of an inflammatory nature. The study did not include children with congenital malformations of the CNS and internal organs, autoimmune and infectious inflammatory diseases of other organs established during the two months preceding the examination.

In the statistical processing of the data obtained, generally accepted methods of variational statistics were used. The reliability of statistical differences was assessed by parametric and non-parametric methods using the criteria of Student (t), Mann - Whitney, Wilcoxon. The differences were considered statistically reliable at a level of significance of at least 95%. To assess the specificity of the original questionnaire we developed to detect gastroduodenal pathology and PP, the CNS conducted a correlation analysis with the determination of the coefficient of Spearman's rank correlation.

Research results

It is believed that immediately after childbirth in the delivery room, newborns should be attached to the mother's breast. These are the children who formed the

control group. The newly studied newborns of the first and second groups after birth were in a state of severe asphyxia and could not be applied to the breast in the delivery room.

Taking into account the severity of the condition, all patients with PP CNS of the first and second groups received food (pasteurized donor milk or baby milk mixtures) through a nasogastric probe. The children of the first group were transferred to natural feeding at the age of three to four weeks, children of the second group due to premature and lack of sucking reflex a little later - at the age of one - one and a half months, but using mother's milk. The nutrition scheme corresponded to the severity of the condition of newborns and the degree of prenatalism.

It is possible that one of the risk factors for the development of inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in such children is the frequent introduction of a nasogastric probe into the stomach, the use of donor milk or adapted mixtures.

We analyzed the duration of natural feeding of children with PP CNS and gastroduodenal pathology .

According to our data, only 15 (14.3%) patients of the first and second groups received natural feeding. Children who did not receive breast milk at all were 25% in the first group, 8% in the second group. 98% of children in the control group were naturally fed ($p > 0.05$ compared to the first and second groups).

It should be noted that in children of the first and second groups who did not receive natural feeding or received it for a short period of time, inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract began from early infancy, that is, from one month of life. On the contrary, naturally fed children have gastrointestinal diseases registered since the sixth to seventh month of life.

Taking into account the severity of the condition during the newborn period, 8 (7.6%) children of the first and 6 (5.7%) children of the second group received parenteral nutrition.

As is known, parenteral nutrition, which is an integral part of intensive nutritional supportive infusion therapy, newborns receive very rarely - according to certain indications.

As the condition of the children improved, they gradually switched to parenteral nutrition. At first, they gradually reduced parenteral feeding and increased enteral feeding. When the amount of breast milk absorbed during enteral administration reached 15 ml, parenteral nutrition was stopped.

When assessing the nature of artificial and mixed feeding, it was established that children of the first and second groups received adapted and unadapted milk mixtures. Analysis of the type of feeding of infants with inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract showed that up to 78.3% of children of the first and second groups were on mixed and artificial feeding.

Children who were naturally fed from birth were transferred to artificial and mixed feeding earlier (from one month).

Our results are confirmed by the data of most authors who associate the development of inflammatory processes of the gastrointestinal tract with artificial feeding from birth or early age . Perhaps in children with PP CNS, especially in premature, there are disorders of the functioning of the enzyme systems of the gastrointestinal tract, which leads to inflammatory processes of the mucous membrane of the digestive tract .

According to most authors, a special role in the formation of the function of the digestive tract in young children belongs to the timely introduction of complementary food .

According to the data we analyzed on the timing of the introduction of complementary food , children with PP CNS and gastroduodenal pathology were administered complementary food earlier than four months (the optimal period recommended by the Institute of Nutrition of the Russian Academy of Sciences). The timing of the introduction of complementary foods was more often violated in the group of premature babies - 27 (25.7%) cases.

Literature data indicate that in mothers against the background of stress (premature birth, the presence of obstetric and extragenital pathology) lactation function decreases. Perhaps the absence or decrease of lactation function in mothers of children of the second group is due to the use of donor pasteurized milk and early introduction of complementary food.

In addition to the severity of the condition and the presence of severe neurological symptoms in the children under study, there was a burdened premorbid background. 23 (21.9%) children of the first group and 32 (30.4%) children of the second group had a combination of pathological background diseases, which was most likely a consequence of diseases of the upper gastrointestinal tract and aggravated gastrointestinal disorders. In the first group, anemia was recorded in 39 (37.1%), rickets - in 19 (18%), dysbacteriosis - in 27 (25.7%). In the second group, these figures were 23 (21.9%), 13 (12.3%) and 18 (17.1%), respectively (Fig. 1). It is possible that these diseases were the result of gastroduodenal pathology, which in turn aggravated the course of the underlying disease. The presence of a large percentage of such deficiency conditions as anemia and rickets in children with digestive disorders is quite understandable by impaired absorption and excessive losses of pathogenetically significant macronutrients. Gastrointestinal disorders caused the development of chronic eating disorders: hypotrophy of the 1st-2nd degree was detected in 14% of children of the first group and in 25% - the second.

In premature babies, the symptoms of gastrointestinal dysfunction were regarded as signs of morphofunctional immaturity of nervous regulation of the digestive organs. This condition aggravates the violation of the motor and digestive functions of the digestive tract.

According to domestic authors, early introduction of complementary foods can negatively affect the development of the child. Analysis of clinical manifestations of gastroduodenal pathology in young children (up to five months) with PP CNS showed that the leading complaints were sighing - 93% and vomiting - 89%. As is known, scurry and vomiting syndrome in young children with PP CNS characterizes

the presence of clinical manifestations and criteria for the severity of hypertensive-hydrocephalic syndrome. However, the clinical manifestations of gastroduodenal pathology in children of the first and second groups differed significantly ($p < 0.05$).

More often, functional disorders of the esophagogastroduodenal zone were found in children of the first group (premom) with PP CNS. This group was dominated by persistent sneezing - 58%, constipation - 72%, vomiting - 54%, less often pain - 15%. These indicators differed significantly from the data of the second group: squagging - 35%, constipation - 38%, vomiting - 35%, pain - 22%.

Bloating was registered in the second group more often (67%) than in the first.

Clinical manifestations of gastroduodenal pathology were analyzed in children from six months to a year. The obtained data are presented in the table. 5. It was established that with age, clinical manifestations decreased almost twice in both the first and second groups. But the majority of children who had persistent squinting and vomiting at the age of six months to a year had pain syndrome and constipation: the first group - 78 and 84%, the second - 67 and 78%, respectively.

Perhaps age-related changes in both the mucous membrane and the enzyme system of the digestive tract affect the transformation of clinical symptoms of gastroduodenal pathology .

Please note: with age in children of the second group (premitional) clinical manifestations of gastroduodenal pathology were much less than in the first group (preminated), but the indicators are unreliable ($p > 0.05$). Children received therapy for intracranial hypertension and hydrocephalus, which temporarily reduced gastro-interstitial dysfunction.

Perinatal CNS damage is more often one of the leading causes of pathological changes in the upper gastrointestinal tract in young children. According to our studies, children of the first and second groups have a high incidence of hypertensive-hydrocephalic syndrome.

Unlike the second group, neurological symptoms were significantly more often detected in the first group

In addition, the dependence of the localization of inflammatory gastrointestinal lesions on age has been established.

Conclusions

The results of the study showed that inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in children with PP CNS, regardless of age, tend to increase. If at an early age there are signs of inflammation of the upper gastrointestinal tract, then with age the digestive glands and lower gastrointestinal tract are involved in the pathological process. There are often lying, vomiting and abdominal pain. Violations of the act of defecation in the form of constipation - the main clinical manifestation in gastrointestinal pathology - 57% of children of the first group and 70% - the second. It is important that children with a history of constipation had persistent sneezing and vomiting in infancy.

The leading clinical syndrome in patients with inflammatory pathology of the upper gastrointestinal tract may indicate the localization of the pathological process. Thus, abdominal pain syndrome in young children with perinatal lesions of the nervous system indicates a distal lesion of the upper digestive tract. Constipation as the main complaint is noted only in patients with gastroduodenitis.

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